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Towards click chemistry: Multicomponent reactions via combinations of name reactions

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Abstract

in this report, we try to show the importance of incorporation of name reactions in the sequential cascade reaction in which significantly decreasing the number of steps towards an ideal and practical multi-step synthesis of natural products as well showing virtually all the advantages already mentioned for “Click Chemistry”. In addition, since the chiral inductions are desired for most of these sequential name reactions, their asymmetric catalyzed reactions were also described.